

Performance of Women Entrepreneurs in Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

This study was cross-sectional research to find out the factors affecting the performance of women entrepreneurs in SMEs of Bangladesh. The specific objectives were to assess women entrepreneurs' business profiles and environmental facilities that affect the performance of their businesses. The performance of 375 women entrepreneurs was assessed in terms of capital invested, revenues earned, expenses incurred, profits made and employment growth. Face to face interviews and phone interviews were the predominant data collection method. In addition to this, the observation method was also used. The research found that women entrepreneurs were mostly young, married, literate, and experienced by ten to twenty years. They were involved mostly in sole proprietorship of small trades and services rather than in manufacturing. Most of them had been suffering from lack of starter capital, access to the capital market, collateral financing, theoretical knowledge, ICT skilled manpower, and organizational supports. The environmental factors were found to have adverse effects on their entrepreneurial success and most of the women entrepreneurs were found dismayed over the political situation, legislation and tax issues. Nonetheless, women entrepreneurs were found to be playing significant roles in reducing poverty and unemployment despite their struggle to balance business, social and personal lives.

Keywords: Women entrepreneur, SME, Bangladesh.

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1.0. INTRODUCTION

Women own about 30% of the total enterprises in OECD countries and about the same ratio holds for the developing countries as well but the scenario seems to have created a plateau in the latter case (OECD, 2012). In Bangladesh, women entrepreneurs are now getting significant attention from the policymakers and one of the reasons for that could be that the female labor force increased at a considerably higher rate (4.6%) than that (1%) of the male labor force (BBS, 2018). However, women entrepreneurs, in comparison to their men competitors, are lagging in terms of their performance. About 12% of the 35.6% of women in the labor force in Bangladesh emerged as entrepreneurs (Ahmed, Hossain & Hossain, 2018). Nonetheless, studies show that female business owners have been contributing more than the male counterpart in minimizing women's poor participation at work (Ahmed, Hossain & Hossain, 2018). Women entrepreneurship is diverse and women are found in business sectors including fashion-rich personal effects, wear and consumption goods (31.8%); agro-processing (10.3%); knitwear and ready-made garments (6.3%); pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and toiletries (3.4%); electronics and electrical goods (2.6%); healthcare (1.7%); light engineering (1.4%); leather goods (1.2%); software development (0.4%); plastic and synthetics (0.3%); education (0.1%); and others (40.3%) (SMEF, 2015). Despite the reality of women's multifold involvements in entrepreneurship, women entrepreneurs still encounter dual responsibilities of managing business and family, much of which is deeply rooted in sociocultural realities and persisting patriarchal norms (Chowdhury, 2009).

In the context that participation of women in entrepreneurial activities in Bangladesh is facing changes such as an increased preference for business by educated women and challenges regarding trade facilitation due to marital status (Ahmed, Hossain & Hossain, 2018), the paper organizes its contents by presenting the objectives, in the beginning, to offer a guideline to the underlying flow of the paper. Related literature is then presented to develop an understanding of the issues that would assist in comprehending the methodology and arguments of this paper. Methodology, findings and conclusions sections then follow in the rest of the paper.

1.1. OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this study was to assess the factors which contribute to women entrepreneur's performance. Deconstruction of the main objective emerged in the following specific objectives.

1. To assess the demographic characteristics of women entrepreneurs
2. To examine their business profiles
3. To appraise environmental factors of supporting and opposing the performances
4. To construct a SWOT matrix
5. To recommend measures for greater participation from women entrepreneurs

The following section presents related literature to understand the realities of women entrepreneurship in Bangladesh.

2.0. LITERATURE REVIEW

The term 'entrepreneur' was first introduced either by Richard Cantillon or Jean-Baptiste Say, though some argue for a different and older origin (Jonsson, 2017). Entrepreneurs are understood as agents who buy means of production at certain prices to combine them into a product that they sell at a particular price. However, entrepreneurship is perceived in several ways by experts (Saxon, 2003). Some consider it a multidisciplinary discourse, whereas psychologists emphasize an individual's inherent attributes, values, and traits as the reasons for becoming an entrepreneur. However, social scientists believe that entrepreneurship emerges through networking with friends, relatives, and associations. Entrepreneurship as a concept was more generalized by Schumpeter (1934) and later by Hagen (1958), creating opportunities for investment and production; establishing an organization capable of introducing non-production processes; developing new capabilities, use of alternative raw materials, innovative new production techniques, and search for new sources of raw materials; and introducing efficient management to run an organization.

The definition of SME varies to the underlying context because it covers a wide range of activities. However, the shared senses around SME implicate that it is a labor-intensive entity and it involves relatively low capital intensity (MIDAS, 2009). Small enterprise refers to the firms and/or businesses which are not a public limited company, and which conform to specific asset-employee criteria presented in Table 1 (Bangladesh Bank, 2010).

Table 1: Asset-Employee Criteria for Small Enterprise

Sectors	Fixed asset other than land and building (BDT)	Employed manpower (not above)
Service	50,000 - 50,00,000	25
Business	50,000 - 50,00,000	25
Industrial	50,000 - 1,50,00,000	50

Source: Bangladesh Bank (2010)

Medium enterprise refers to the establishments and/or firms which are not a public limited company, and which conform to specific asset-employee criteria presented in Table 2 (Bangladesh Bank, 2010).

Table 2: Asset-Employee Criteria for Medium Enterprise

Sectors	Fixed asset other than land and building (BDT)	Employed manpower (not above)
Service	50,00,000 - 10,00,00,000	50
Business	50,00,000 - 10,00,00,000	50
Industrial	1,50,00,000 - 20,00,00,000	150

Source: Bangladesh Bank (2010)

While Bangladesh Bank (2010) has the above specific criteria to define small and medium enterprises, IFC (2009), as per the Ministry of Industry of Bangladesh, classifies small businesses as entities involved in manufacturing with fixed assets valued at less than BDT15 million excluding the value of land, and as entities involved in nonmanufacturing with fewer than 25 workers. In the same spirit, it classifies medium businesses as entities involved in manufacturing with fixed assets valued between BDT15 million and BDT100 million excluding the value of land, and as entities involved in nonmanufacturing with workers between 25 and 100 (IFC, 2009).

Women entrepreneurs are celebrated today, and historical evidence shows women's involvement in business even in early times. However, history also shows that women were not welcomed in the business world in the first place (Gay, 2016). Women entrepreneurs encounter a variety of problems during the creation and expansion of the business that has effects on their performance (OECD, 1997 & 2004). There is a lack of data about entrepreneurial obstacles for women's entry or success in the business and this makes policy formulation difficult (UNIDO, 2001). It is also argued that due to persisting patriarchy, little attention has been directed to the female entrepreneurship (OECD, 2004). Researchers found that mainstream entrepreneurship theories, researches, policies, and programs tend to be 'men streamed' and overlook the specific needs of women entrepreneurs (OECD, 2004). Thus, research tools used to examine female entrepreneurship largely drawn from studies based on the experiences and characteristics of men (Brush *et al.*, 2006). Researches have been perceived to be gender-biased paying little attention to the specific needs of women entrepreneurs (Brush *et al.*, 1999), resulting in women entrepreneurs getting marginalized in mainstream entrepreneurship research (OECD, 2004).

Women have been involved in the different areas of business including retailing, education, health care, handicraft, beauty parlors, block printing and boutiques, bakery and fast food, doll making, tailoring, fabrics paint and interior decoration. Women also own non-traditional initiatives including computer training centers,

leather goods making, and fish culture. Rural women are found involved in cattle and poultry rearing, rice husking, spice making, imitation ornament trading, pickle making, and other micro-businesses. The majority of them meet the essential criteria of entrepreneurship. However, most of the women in Bangladesh remain underutilized and women represent only 10% of the total business entrepreneurs; whereas women in developed economies own more than 30% of all businesses (Parvin, Jinrong & Rahman, 2012). Among the total economically active population of 53.5 million in the country, 40 million males and females are working in the field of services and business sectors. Out of them, only 13.5 million employed workforces are female. Women enterprises are usually small in size and generally, short-term loans are more widely used for those, which has an average size of BDT0.3 million.

Entrepreneurial skills and collateral capacities are identified by some studies as key factors for success in entrepreneurship (Rahman, 1995; Momen & Begum, 2006; Afrin, Islam & Ahmed, 2008). Saleh (1995) found that inadequate cash flows, marketing deficits and discriminating treatment from support service agencies create obstacles to the entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. Hossain and Rahman (1999) found that the lack of working capital is one of the most serious problems and about 60% of women entrepreneurs seriously suffer from insufficient working capital. Rural women entrepreneurs compared to their male counterparts neither get social recognition nor own assets to use as collateral to get financial supports which restrain their motivation in business. It is argued that high-interest rates of borrowing, complex government regulations, small domestic market, significant collateral requirement, and lack of technically skilled workers are the key impediments to better performances of women entrepreneurs in SMEs (Chowdhury, 2011). It is also claimed that women entrepreneurs lack information and do not get proper support from relevant institutions because of corruption in supporting organizations (Rabbani & Chowdhury, 2013).

Certain personal attributes and socio-economic background of the entrepreneurs are also identified as the key factors for entrepreneurial success or failure (Aktaruddin, 1999 & 2000). It was found that 75% of the rural women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh face marketing problems for their products due to the persisting conservative social norms and practices (Aktaruddin, 2003). Lack of knowledge, education, and technical training were also found affecting women entrepreneurs' business operations (Habibullah, 1987; Hossain & Rahman, 1999). Faruk (2008) found that nearly 78% of the rural women only had an entrepreneurial experience of fewer than three years. Lack of basic education, knowledge, training, and experience are found to seriously affect the efficiency of women entrepreneurs. Marital status is identified as another determinant of success for women entrepreneurs. Unmarried women enjoyed a higher probability to succeed in their entrepreneurial initiatives than married women (Kamal & Zunaid, 2011). Some studies identified five factors that affect women entrepreneurs' performance and those include access to finance, access to market, access to training, access to networks and access to policymakers (UNECE, 2004; Haq, 2000). Some studies revealed the mediating relationships between opportunity and women entrepreneurs' performance (Tata & Prasad, 2008; Baron & Shane, 2005) while a few other studies revealed the persisting moderating relationships between attitude to taking risk and women entrepreneurs' performance (Crisp & Turner, 2007; Vob & Muller, 2009). Violence against women was argued as a major factor that affected both the personal and occupational performance of women entrepreneurs (Zaman, 1999).

Performance usually refers to the act of doing something successfully with one's distinguished or specialized knowledge. Performance can be conceptualized, operationalized and measured in different ways (Srinivasan, Woo & Cooper, 1994). Entrepreneurs' performance can usually be understood by their survival, growth in employees, and profitability in businesses (Lerner, Brush & Hisrich, 1997). Victor H. Vroom explained performance as the function of one's ability, motivation, and the environment in where s/he acts. Performance can be measured by annual sales, the number of employees, return on sales, growth in sales, and growth in employee numbers (Brush & Vanderwerf, 1992). It can also be measured in terms of human capital factors

including education, experience, skill, personal goal, motivation, and network affiliation (Lerner *et al.*, 1997). The entrepreneurial performance is also related to the desire for growth and ownership of multiple businesses (Rosa *et al.*, 1996).

The basic factors that affect entrepreneurial performance can be divided into two broad categories – economic and social (Samiti 2006 & Tan, 2000). The economic factors include competition in the market, access to the information, availability of raw material, cost of capital or finance, gathering marketing knowledge, acquisition of production and/or storage space, construction of infrastructure, adequacy of power supply and exposition of business training. The social factors include social acceptability, having contacts outside, prejudice and class bias, society's outlook, and attitude of the workforce. It can be argued that the different types of programs and policies related to entrepreneurship development also have an impact on performance.

3.0. METHODOLOGY

A quantitative approach was used to address the research objectives. While primary data was collected through interviewing women entrepreneurs using a comprehensive questionnaire, secondary data were collected from books, articles, and reports. A sample survey of 375 women entrepreneurs was conducted. This sample was selected out of the women entrepreneurs enlisted by eight renowned organizations that work as a watchdog or supporting institutions for women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh. The organizations include SME Foundation, Micro Industries Development Assistance and Services (MIDAS), BRAC and five others. Women entrepreneurs both in rural and urban areas, irrespective of the size, type, location, and nature of their businesses, were contacted in person for data collection. They were chosen irrespective of their age, experience, education, and training. The sampling process is presented in brief in Table 3.

Table 3: Sampling Approach

Step	Process	Details
1	Population identification	Women entrepreneurs were identified from SME Foundation, Department of Women Affairs of the Government of Bangladesh (GoB), MIDAS, Palli Karma-Sahayak Foundation (PKSF), Women Entrepreneur Association of Bangladesh (WEAB), Grameen Bank, BRAC, and Bangladesh Small and Cottage Industries Corporation (BSCIC).
2	Population segregation	The population was divided based on the nature of entrepreneurs' business, including manufacturing, trading, service, Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and handicrafts.
3	Sample stratification	Two types of population segments were identified: administrative divisions and districts.
4	Sampling technique	A purposive random sampling technique was used.
5	Sample size	The total sample size was 375, where each selected division comprised 20-30 samples and each district comprised 5-10 samples.

Source: Authors' construct

The population of the study was divided into five segments based on the nature of business and they include manufacturing, trading, services, NGOs, and handicrafts (cottages). Respondents were randomly selected from the district level population to conform to the predetermined size of the sample. It was at least 20 respondents for each division and five respondents for each district. Using purposive random sampling, a total of 375 respondents were selected from seven divisions and 34 districts (Table 4). This sampling technique was used because i) simple random sampling risks lack representation of different demographic

characteristics, ii) facilities, opportunities, and infrastructural supports vary at division and district levels, and iii) access to women entrepreneurs was sometimes found challenging.

Table 4: Geographic Distribution of Sample

Name of the division and respective total sample	Name of the district	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondent	Cumulative total
Dhaka, 65	Dhaka	31	8.27	8.27
	Gazipur	10	2.67	10.93
	Narayangonj	10	2.67	13.60
	Manikgonj	8	2.13	15.73
	Faridpur	6	1.60	17.33
Chattogram, 65	Chittagong	30	8.00	25.33
	Comilla	10	2.67	28.00
	Noakhali	10	2.67	30.67
	Cox's Bazar	10	2.67	33.33
	Rangamati	5	1.33	34.67
Rajshahi, 55	Rajshahi	30	8.00	42.67
	Bogra	10	2.67	45.33
	Sirajgonj	5	1.33	46.67
	Pabna	5	1.33	48.00
	Joypurhat	5	1.33	49.33
Khulna, 45	Khulna	20	5.33	54.67
	Jessore	10	2.67	57.33
	Bagerhat	5	1.33	58.67
	Satkhira	5	1.33	60.00
	Narail	5	1.33	61.33
Sylhet, 45	Sylhet	25	6.67	68.00
	Moulvibazar	10	2.67	70.67
	Habigonj	5	1.33	72.00
	Sunamgonj	5	1.33	73.33
Barisal, 50	Barishal	25	6.67	80.00
	Patuakhali	7	1.87	81.87
	Pirojpur	5	1.33	83.20
	Bhola	8	2.13	85.33
	Jhalokathi	5	1.33	86.67
Rangpur, 50	Rangpur	30	8.00	94.67
	Dinajpur	5	1.33	96.00
	Gaibandha	5	1.33	97.33
	Nilphamary	5	1.33	98.67
	Lalmonirhat	5	1.33	100.00
		375		

Source: Authors' construct

This cross-sectional study is underpinned by descriptive statistics of dependent and independent variables. The dependent variable of this study was women entrepreneur's performance which was measured in terms of capital, revenue, expenditure, profit, and employee growth of their business entities. The independent

variables were factors that affect performance, women entrepreneur's characteristics, characteristics of the business, and external environment. Among the variables, entrepreneurial training and education played a moderating role, whereas enactment of government policies and programs, an invention of sophisticated technologies, and the role of trade organizations played an intervening role as these persisted for the time being and could be controlled. It was hypothesized that all these independent, moderating, and intervening variables had impacts on the performance (dependent variable) of women entrepreneurs involved in SME. It was useful in establishing a causal relationship among the independent variables and the dependent variable where the former includes personal characteristics, business profiles, marketing strategies, entrepreneurial attributes, services and assistance, and environmental factors, and the latter comprises entrepreneurs' performance.

Figure 1: Factors Affecting the Entrepreneur's Performance

Source: Authors' construct

4.0. RESEARCH FINDINGS

The majority of the women entrepreneurs suffer from low social status, insufficient education and training, and inadequate supports from the government and non-government agencies. Early researches on entrepreneurship in Bangladesh shared similar findings where entrepreneurs were found to have poor educational qualifications (Farouk, 1983; Rahman, 1989). There exist inequalities in terms of rights and benefits. Women's contributions, particularly in household activities, are neither accepted nor recognized as salaried jobs. The challenges women entrepreneurs face can be associated with the characteristics of the respective business and the environment where women need to perform. Demographic attributes such as age, sex, education, and experience play a significant role to be successful entrepreneurs. Nature and types of businesses, capital investment, access to markets, use of technologies also contribute to the performances of women entrepreneurs. The external environment includes social, economic, technological, legal, political dimensions; and it plays a significant role in influencing business performance. Women have no easy access to the marketplace, technologies, finance, support services, and communication networks. Information paucity is another drawback for policy implications and building capacities of women entrepreneurs. The limited access to the information-sharing system impedes women entrepreneurs' knowledge of organizational

management. Unlike men, women entrepreneurship is more complex a phenomenon as women have to balance their family and business life simultaneously.

Women entrepreneurs in the formal and informal sectors of Bangladesh are often neglected by society. Inequalities between women and men exist in terms of opportunities, rights, and benefits. A coherent attempt from public and private bodies is badly needed to remove these constraints. Women entrepreneurs' lack of information is mostly caused by limited access to the learning process, knowledge sharing, business planning, social networks, and concerned authorities. Despite many barriers, women entrepreneurs are taking challenges to continue their hard work in a male-dominated, competitive and complex environment. However, their performance was challenged by a myriad of factors prevailing in the external and internal environments. These factors include internal factors such as demographic, business, management and networking characteristics, as well as environmental factors such as political, economic, social, technological, and legal situations, local resources and human resources. Analyses of the major factors that affect women entrepreneurs' performance are presented below.

4.1. Demographic Factors

Women entrepreneurs in SMEs of Bangladesh were found relatively younger (Table A1). Most of them were found in the age group of 21-39 years. This may indicate that women entrepreneurship is a newly populated phenomenon in our society. Most of them became entrepreneurs in the last two decades (Table A2). About 96% of them were found to have less than 20 years of experience. Educated women could gain more confidence in entrepreneurial activities because of their academic involvement and formal and informal networking. Most of the women entrepreneurs were found relatively educated (Table A3). About 90% of the entrepreneurs were found married (Table A4). This picture looked different when women were involved in paid occupations in the garment and other service sectors where unmarried women were preferred. Referring to women entrepreneurs' previous occupation, 47% were found housewives (Table A5). Women from small families were found relatively more involved in business or entrepreneurial activities (Table A6). About 35% of the women entrepreneurs were found highly educated and 66% of them completed higher secondary level. More than two-thirds (69%) women entrepreneurs had at least one business ancestor in the family, i.e. their husband or relative had an experience of business (Table A7). The women entrepreneurs were encouraged by their husbands' or relatives' occupations. A significant number of women entrepreneurs (72.53%) were found who used to receive assistance from their husbands and/or relatives (Table A8 and Table A9). The demographic characteristics of women entrepreneurs are presented in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Demographic Characteristics of Women Entrepreneurs

Description of variable	Value	Respondents	Percentage
Age	20-39 Year	231	61.60
Education	HSC and higher degrees	249	66.40
Experience	More than 10 year	164	44.00
Previous status	Housewives	269	71.73
Marital status	Married	338	90.13
Family size	Less than five people	247	66.87
Husband/guardian's occupation	Business	258	68.80
Supported by husband/guardian	Yes	272	72.53

Source: Authors' construct

4.2. Business Factors

The women entrepreneurs were found to have some unique characteristics related to business. They were largely engaged in trading and commerce, manufacturing, livestock, and services-oriented businesses (Table B1). Most of the women entrepreneurs (61%) were the founder of their businesses (Table B2). Almost three fourth of them were the sole proprietors (Table B3). Most of the women entrepreneurs had been operating only in the local markets for the trading of garments, showpieces, aesthetics, and domestic utensils. Among them, 16.8% were involved in foreign trade (Table B8). In regulatory provisions, about 85% of the women entrepreneurs had trade licenses, about 63% had to pay income taxes, and 44% of them had the VAT registration (Table B4). Although about two-thirds of them got the initial capital from their husbands and/or close relatives, almost 40% of them had a motivation to become a self-employed person, 15% had come for the sake of family needs, one-tenth had no alternative option, and only 7% had the aspiration to get involved in the business which was mainstream for men (Table B5). About three fourth of women entrepreneurs had a one-year business plan (Table B6) and 69% of women entrepreneurs prepare their business plan (Table B7). Nearly one-third of them had some sorts of trade fair participation experience and about 17% of them were involved in export and/or import businesses (Table B8). Business-related characteristics of women entrepreneurs are presented in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Business Related Characteristics of Women Entrepreneurs

Description of variables	Characteristics	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Business nature	Trading and commerce	180	48.00	339 respondents, out of 375 were considered. They were not mutually exclusive.
Business founder	Herself	231	61.60	
Ownership	Sole proprietor	270	72.00	
Reason to come into the business	Self-employment	150	40.00	
Business plan	2 years or less	282	84.00	

Source: Authors’ construct

4.3. Capital Management Factors

Most of the women entrepreneurs suffered to arrange their initial capital. The major problems related to initial capital included insufficient capital, inadequate loan amount, informal sources, and paucity of information (Table C1). They also faced problems with managing the initial loan or advance or credit and the issues were related to high-interest rate, complex loan procedure, and requirements for fixed assets as collaterals for credit (Table C2). About three fourth (74%) of the women entrepreneurs were primarily funded by their husbands or relatives (Table C3). About 60% of them were funded by banks whereas about 16% of them were funded by either NGOs or government organizations (Table C4). Almost 90% of the women entrepreneurs started their businesses with less than BDT500,000 (Table C5) and their ending business capital was up to BDT5000,000 (Table C6). Although 50% of them have a monthly current revenue of BDT400,000 or above (Table C8), almost two-thirds (62%) of the women entrepreneurs had reported that they could initially earn up to BDT100,000 only (Table C7). Their average business worth was up to BDT 4 million and the average debt-equity ratio was 1:3. The investment profile of the women entrepreneurs is presented in Table 7 below.

Table 7: Investment Profile of Women Entrepreneurs

Description of variables	Value	Respondents	Percentage
Insufficient savings	-	285	84.82
Interest rate is high	-	270	75.00
Primary source	Family	245	65.33
Bank loan/advance	-	195	60.19
Initial capital	Less than BDT500,000	289	77.06
Current capital	More than BDT1000,000	271	72.84
Initial revenues	Less than BDT100,000	215	62.14
Current revenues	More than 400,000	178	50.00

Source: Authors' construct

4.4. Marketing and Human Resource Management Factors

The major marketing strategies of the women entrepreneurs were found to deliver quality products at market price or lower price (Table D1). More than half of them (53.6%) were following the markup pricing method (Table D2). Almost two-thirds of women entrepreneurs (65.60%) carried out their marketing activities all by themselves (Table D3). The majority of them prefer newspapers (55.56%) and signboards or billboards (61.11%) as the advertisement mediums (Table D4). However, the television was found as the least preferred (5.56%) advertising medium which could be associated with the overall size of their businesses (Table D4). Major sales promotion offers used by the women entrepreneurs were price reduction, seasonal outlet, gifts, and free delivery to the customers (Table D5). However, over half (53.6%) of them did not use any kind of promotional offer (Table D5). Women entrepreneurs gathered market information from three major sources which were customers (54%), suppliers (10%), and personal sources (30%) (Table D6). About half of the women entrepreneurs do not have any target customers; only 10% of them conduct market research, and only 30% had trade fair participation and used a personal selling approach (Table D7). More than 90% of women entrepreneurs have product showroom. Almost one-third of the women entrepreneurs could arrange home delivery for their sold goods. Only about one third (32%) women entrepreneurs invested in an advertisement. The major marketing problems faced by the women entrepreneurs (55%) were about the high expense of marketing, roads and transportation problem while the second most frequent problems were transportation problems and lack of information and/or knowledge (Table D8).

Their average employee size was less than 10 and in most cases, the number of female employees was five or less. About 42% of women entrepreneurs informed that they had more than 10 employees for their business and only 36% of them had more than five women employees (Table D9 and Table D10). About 71% of women entrepreneurs give less than BDT5000 as the minimum salary for their employees whereas only a few (7%) of them provide more than BDT20000 as the maximum salary for their employees (Table D11 and Table D12). More than 80% of the women entrepreneurs provide incentives to their employees and only one-third of them provide bonuses and overtime as the major incentives to their employees (Table D13). Major marketing and management skills of women entrepreneurs are presented in Table 8 below.

Table 8: Marketing and Management Skills of the Women Entrepreneurs

Component	Details	Respondents	Percentage
Key marketing person	Self	246	65.60
Major promotion	Sales promotion (price reduction)	141	37.60
Advertisement media	Newspapers	150	40.00
Market source	Customers + Self Experiment	315	84.00

Personal selling	-	114	30.00
Trade fair participation	-	111	30.00
Foreign trade experience	-	63	17.00
Initial revenue	Less than BDT100,000	215	62.14
Current revenue	More than BDT500,000	163	45.46
Initial profit	Less than BDT20,000	244	65.06
Current profit	More than BDT50,000	72	19.83
Initial employee	Less than 10	355	95.95
Current employee	More than 10	158	42.13
Current women employee	More than 5	135	36.00
Employees' monthly minimum salary	Less than BDT5,000	267	71.20
Employees' monthly maximum salary	More than BDT20,000	27	7.20
Provide incentives	Bonus and overtime	121	32.77

Source: Authors' construct

4.5. Networking and Communication Factors

Women entrepreneurs possessed distinctive competencies in the areas of Management Information System (MIS) and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT). About 47% of them had personal computers (PC) (Table E1) while about 77% of them had less than five PCs in their business units. About 56% of them used the internet, 46% had personal e-mail but only 21% of them had their business websites (Table E2). Only 41% of women entrepreneurs used the computer for their accounting and bookkeeping purposes (Table E3). Despite different types of skills requirements for their activities, about 65% of the women entrepreneurs were found satisfied with their workers' efficiency. Only 45% of the women entrepreneurs admitted that they improved compliant working conditions. The major ICT related issues identified by the women entrepreneurs were: high price, frequent changes in technologies, lack of related education and knowledge, lack of training, and complex maintenance (Table E4). ICT usage profile of the women entrepreneurs is presented in Table 9 below.

Table 9: ICT Usage Profile

Category	Respondents	Percentage
Owens less than five PCs	216	77.42
Uses Internet	210	56.00
Uses e-mail account for business purposes	174	46.40
Uses own business website	78	20.80

Source: Authors' construct

4.6. External Environmental Factors

In terms of external environmental factors, such as threats, women entrepreneurs were found considerably dissatisfied over the civil and political environment. Law and order situation and policy regarding SME interest rates were found at the most dissatisfactory level for them. The overall assessment of the impacts of civil and political factors was found negative (Table F1). For the economic environment, the business infrastructure, cost of raw materials, and inflation rate were found to create negative impacts on women entrepreneurs. The overall impacts of the economic factors were not found favorable to them (Table F2). In

terms of social perspectives, women entrepreneurs had little dissatisfaction with recognition, while they were nearly satisfied with gender parities and social securities (Table F3). The overall impacts of the social environment were found satisfactory to the respondents (Table F3). Concerning the technological environment, women entrepreneurs were found satisfied with the cost and technical skills requirements (Table F4). The overall impacts of the technological influences were found nearly satisfactory (Table F4). Women entrepreneurs were found mostly indifferent to legal factors related to entrepreneurship. Among the legal factors, the cost of legal supports was found relatively more dissatisfactory (Table F5). The overall impact of the legal environment was found indifferent (neither satisfactory nor unpleasant) (Table F5). In terms of environment and local resources, women entrepreneurs were found satisfied with the availability of raw materials, natural resources, and climatic conditions. The overall impacts of the environment and local resources were found nearly satisfactory to the women entrepreneurs (Table F6). Regarding human resources, women entrepreneurs were found comparatively less satisfied with the cost of human resources than the availability and skills of the workers. The overall impacts of the human resource factors were found nearly considerably satisfactory (Table F7).

4.7. Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT) Analysis

Women entrepreneurs in Bangladesh possess strengths and enjoy opportunities, despite their weaknesses and the existence of threats they need to encounter. However, for better performance, they had to maximize their strengths and opportunities to minimize their weaknesses and threats. A summary of the SWOT analysis regarding the women entrepreneurs' performance is presented below in Table 10.

Table 10: SWOT of Women Entrepreneurs

	Strengths	Opportunities
Scopes for maximization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Entrepreneurial education 2. Entrepreneurial experience 3. Motivation for innovation 4. Entrepreneurial ancestors 5. Availability of starter capital 6. Sources for starter capital 7. Availability of collaterals 8. Good managerial capacities 9. Good marketing capacities 10. Social networking capacities 11. Supervision capacity 12. Business planning capacity 13. ICT capacity 14. Accounting capacity 15. Employees relations 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Government and NGO assistances 2. Tax rebates/redemption 3. Low cost of investment 4. Liberal market competition 5. Social safety/acceptances 6. Access to modern technologies 7. Skills for modern technologies 8. Benefits of industrial laws 9. Availability of natural resources 10. Favorable business climates 11. Skills and availability of HR 12. Gender parities 13. Workforce availabilities 14. Use of infrastructure 15. Micro-Finance Institutions / development programs
	Weaknesses	Threats
Scopes for minimization	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lack of starter capital 2. Poor relationships with stakeholders 3. Lack of training/information 4. Use of legacy technology 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Political unrest 2. Adverse business policies 3. High cost for capital 4. Collaterals and interest rate 5. Bureaucratic complexities 6. Tough market competition

<p>5. Lack of land and building ownership</p> <p>6. Lack of social participation</p> <p>7. Lack of workers' affinities</p> <p>8. Lack of ICT skills</p> <p>9. Lack of supervision</p> <p>10. Poor marketing skills</p> <p>11. Lack of business ideas</p> <p>12. Lack of business planning</p>	<p>7. Inflation/ low purchasing power</p> <p>8. The high cost of raw materials</p> <p>9. Lack of infrastructures/utilities</p> <p>10. Lack of social recognition</p> <p>11. Need for high cost and sophisticated technological skills</p> <p>12. Lack of access to legal support</p> <p>13. Lack of raw materials</p> <p>14. Lack of skilled workforce</p>
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Source: Authors' construct

5.0. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Most of the Bangladeshi women entrepreneurs were found young, married, educated, engaged in full-time entrepreneurship, and supported by family members, in most cases by their husbands. Though women were involved in various business sectors, they had better opportunities in the manufacturing and services sectors. Entrepreneurial training and education helped women entrepreneurs to build confidence. However, the dearth of entrepreneurial orientation and motivational role models are persisting realities that could have influenced women entrepreneurs becoming more innovative, creative, and risk-taker. Innovativeness would enable women entrepreneurs to embrace new technology and becoming risk takers so that they could go after large-scale investments.

Women's experiences in resource mobilization increased their ability of decision making. However, the lack of working capital considerably affected women entrepreneurs' performance. They had also been suffering from lack of marketing training for foreign trade and overseas exposition and were found dependent on other people for marketing activities such as advertising, sales promotion, trade fair participation, and marketing research. Most of the women entrepreneurs put emphasis on the lower priced-bulk production rather than on the quality of products to further their market expansion. Unskilled human capital was another hindrance for women entrepreneurs' performance. Only a few of them were found able to use the internet and had business websites of their own. This led women entrepreneurs to encounter communication and networking challenges. They perceived communication technologies as an expensive option which was hard for them to operate. One reason for this operating challenge was the high pace of rapid changes in technology.

Women entrepreneurs' performance gets affected by the high-interest rate for borrowing, stringent collateral policy, poor law and order situation, and bureaucratic red tapes. Moreover, economic factors such as inflation rate, cost of raw materials, infrastructural rarities also create problems for them to perform well. The dearth of raw materials, high cost of labor, scarcity of skilled workforce, and high cost of legal support services are the other factors that affect women entrepreneurs' performance. The research evidence that women entrepreneurs are weak in business management and marketing, and therefore they need to build capacity in business planning, marketing, accounting and bookkeeping, ICT, e-commerce, and regulatory processes. Instances of public training were found insufficient despite training in some selected areas organized by a few NGOs. Despite the gendered realities and a range of factors that affected women entrepreneurs' performance, women entrepreneurs had considerably been contributing to the development of the country mostly through employment generation and gender mainstreaming. This is because they prioritized the inclusion of more female workers. These women entrepreneurs have also been contributing to their family expenditure and savings.

Women's entrepreneurial involvement is not only a means of economic survival for them and the respective workforces but also is one of the change agents that brings in positive social impacts. For them to contribute as the change agent, they require multifarious facilities and cooperation from both the Government and NGOs (GoB, 2005). Based on the findings of this research, the following recommendations are made for policymakers and the respective key stakeholders.

1. SME Foundation and Bangladesh Bank jointly can operate a comprehensive training institute to provide services related to career research cell, library, and online web portal. These could actively coordinate women entrepreneurs. These initiatives can identify role models in respective sectors and disseminate their best practices, achievements, and related information. Such orientation may help to embed confidence, courage, will-power, risk-taking attitude, creativity and innovativeness in the minds of the current and potential women entrepreneurs.
2. SME Foundation can develop and maintain a knowledge cell on product design and business ideas, for dissemination among women entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurs across the country can exchange technological know-how, experiential insights, and related information to upgrade their product design, ideas, and planning.
3. Development bodies of the GoB can incorporate and focus women's entrepreneurial dimensions in their programs and policies to empower particularly the rural women by creating convenient business involvements in agro-based and cottage industries. These bodies can also facilitate supplying utility services such as gas and electric power. Steps should be taken to extend marketing assistance to women entrepreneurs for the development, promotion, and sales of their products. To facilitate women entrepreneurs' efforts and to develop their marketing efficiencies, a special pocket for women SMEs can be developed within the Export Processing Zone.
4. Bangladesh Bank can suggest MFIs to lower the interest rate for SME borrowing taking that down to a single-digit to allow more women to manage a start-up capital. It can also devise a convenient loan sanctioning procedure and suggest that to respective institutions. The government can increase the ceiling for minimum taxable income, announce tax holiday facilities, and reduce various custom duties on foreign trade for women entrepreneurs, which can bring positive changes in women entrepreneurship in Bangladesh and offer direct and indirect benefits.

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Appendix A

Table A1: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Age

Age group	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
20 – 29	99	26.40	26.40
30 – 39	132	35.20	61.60
40 – 49	115	30.67	92.27
50- 59	25	6.67	98.93
60- 69	4	1.07	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A2: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Experience

Years of	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
1—10	211	56.00	56.00
11—20	143	38.00	94.00
21—30	18	5.00	99.00
31—above	3	1.00	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A3: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Educational Qualification

Qualification	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Honors (3	37	9.87	10.00

Degree or Bachelor	95	25.33	35.20
HSC	117	31.20	66.40
SSC	60	16.00	82.40
Secondary (class VI-	55	14.67	97.07
Primary (Class I-V)	7	1.87	98.93
Nil	4	1.07	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A4: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Marital Status

Marital status	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Married	338	90.13	90.13
Unmarried	23	6.13	96.27
Widow	11	2.93	99.20
Other	3	0.80	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A5: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by the Previous Status

Occupation	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Nil	19	5.07	5.07
Housewives	269	71.73	76.80
Student	47	12.53	89.33
Teacher	16	4.27	93.60
Private jobs	8	2.13	95.73
Public jobs	5	1.33	97.07
Business workers	11	2.93	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A6: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Family Size

Family members	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
One	23	6.13	6.13
Two	24	6.40	12.53
Three	91	24.27	36.80
Four	109	29.07	65.87
Five	89	23.73	89.60
Six	33	8.80	98.40
Seven and above	6	1.60	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A7: Women Entrepreneurs by their Guardians'/Husbands' Occupations

Occupational	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Nil	14	3.73	3.73
Business	264	70.40	74.13
Private jobs	49	13.07	87.02
Public jobs	17	4.53	91.55
Others	31	8.45	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table A8: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Entrepreneurship Heredity

Relations	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Husband	210	79.55	264 respondents had entrepreneur/s in their family, respondents were mutually inclusive, more than one response have been considered. The cumulative percentage is less than 100.
Father	36	13.64	
Mother	9	3.41	
In-laws	30	11.36	
Uncle/aunts	15	5.68	
Others	9	3.41	

Table A9: Women Entrepreneurs by their Family Supports

Supporting individual	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Husband	14	3.73	3.73
Relative	258	68.80	72.53
Others	49	13.07	85.60
Total	375	100.00	

Appendix B

Table B1: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Types of Business

Type of business	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Trading and commerce	180	48.00	48.00
Manufacturing and	52	13.87	61.87
Services delivery	96	25.60	87.47
Livestock/hatchery	35	9.33	96.80
NGOs / cooperatives	12	3.20	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table B2: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Founding Role

Founder's identity	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Self	231	61.60	61.60
Husband/family	93	24.80	86.40
Father/mother/brother	15	4.00	90.40
Self with others outside the	36	9.60	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table B3: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Types of Ownership

Nature of ownership	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Sole proprietorship	270	72.00	72.00
Partnership	85	22.67	94.67
Cooperative	17	4.53	99.20
Joint venture/company	3	0.80	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table B4: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Trade license, Tax, and VAT

Categories	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Trade licenses	318	84.80	Respondents are not mutually exclusive. The total respondents were 375.
Income taxes	236	62.93	
VAT registration	165	44.00	

Table B5: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs' by Reasons for Involvement

Reasons	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Absence of other alternatives	39	10.40	10.40
Self-employment for earning	150	40.00	50.40
To serve humanity (women)	75	20.00	70.40
Seeking solvency for the family	57	15.20	85.60
To fulfill dream/desire	27	7.20	92.80
To avail as the traditional	27	7.20	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table B6: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Business Planning Horizons

Planning period	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
1 year	246	73.00	Respondents are mutually exclusive. 36 respondents (10%) reported that they do not plan for business.
2 years	36	11.00	
3 years or more	57	17.00	
Total	339	100.00	

Table B7: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Business Plan Formulation

Plan formulator's	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Experts	21	6.00	Respondents are mutually exclusive. The only key planner has been considered for each respondent. 36 respondents reported that they had no business plan.
Self	234	69.00	
Husband/relatives	60	18.00	
Employees/officials	24	7.00	
Total	339	100.00	

Table B8: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Other Marketing Strategies

Marketing efforts	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Foreign trade participation	63	16.80	Respondents are mutually exclusive. The total respondents were 375.
Trade fair participation	111	29.60	
Personal selling adoption	114	30.40	
Product research	36	9.60	

Appendix C

Table C1: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Capital Generation Problems

Types of problems	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Insufficient savings	285	84.82	Responses are mutually inclusive. 39 of the respondents reported that they had no problem.
Insufficient loan amount	246	73.21	
Information paucity	132	39.29	
Lack of informal source	45	13.39	

Table C2: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Initial Loan/Advance/Credit Problems

Types of problems	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
The interest rate was high	270	75.00	Respondents were mutually inclusive. 37 respondents (10%) were reported to have no initial capital generation problem.
Credit procedure was complex	135	37.50	
Need for fixed assets as	114	31.67	
More documentation needed for	93	25.83	
Bribe was required	51	14.17	
Experience requirements	39	10.83	

Table C3: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Source of Initial Capital

Source of initial	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative	Remarks
Self	101	26.93	26.93	Respondents are mutually exclusive. Only major investment source has been considered.
Husband/family	144	38.40	65.33	
Relatives	32	8.53	73.87	
Friends and others	18	4.80	78.67	
Institutions	80	21.33	100.00	
Total	375	100.00		

Table C4: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Source of Credit

Sources of credit	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Supplier's credit (cash and kind)	126	38.89	Respondents are mutually inclusive.
banks	195	60.19	
NGOs	54	16.67	
Government organizations	51	15.74	

Table C5: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Monthly Initial Capital

Capital ranges (BDT in thousand)	Respondent	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Over 0 - less or equal to 50	113	30.38	30.38
Over 50 - less or equal to 100	66	17.74	48.12
Over 100 - less or equal to 150	15	4.03	52.15
Over 150 - less or equal to 200	51	13.71	65.86
Over 200 - less or equal to 250	3	0.81	66.67
Over 250 - less or equal to 300	23	6.18	72.85
Over 300 - less or equal to 350	3	0.81	73.66
Over 350 - less or equal to 400	13	3.49	77.15
Over 400 - less or equal to 450	3	0.81	77.96
Over 450 - less or equal to 500	43	11.56	89.52
Over 500	39	10.48	100.00
Total	372	100.00	

Table C6: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Ending Monthly Capital

Capital ranges (BDT in thousand)	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Over 100 - less or equal to 1000	106	28.49	28.49
Over 1000 - less or equal to 2000	120	32.26	60.75
Over 2000 - less or equal to 3000	63	16.94	77.69
Over 3000 - less or equal to 4000	19	5.11	82.80
Over 4000 - less or equal to 5000	29	7.80	90.59
Over 5000 - less or equal to 6000	6	1.61	92.20
Over 6000	29	7.80	100.00
Total	372	100.00	

Table C7: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Monthly Initial Revenues/Incomes

Revenue ranges (BDT in	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Over 0 - less or equal to 50	132	38.15	38.15
Over 50 - less or equal to 100	83	23.99	62.14
Over 100 - less or equal to	68	19.65	81.79
Over 150 - less or equal to	20	5.78	87.57
Over 200 - less or equal to	21	6.07	93.64
Over 250 - less or equal to	3	0.87	94.51
Over 300	19	5.49	100.00
Total	346	100.00	

Table C8: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Ending Monthly Revenues

Revenue ranges (BDT in	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Over 0 - less or equal to 100	10	2.81	2.81
Over 100 - less or equal to	37	10.39	13.20
Over 200 - less or equal to	44	12.36	25.56
Over 300 - less or equal to	87	24.44	50.00
Over 400 - less or equal to	15	4.21	54.21
Over 500 - less or equal to	46	12.92	67.13
Over 600 - less or equal to	22	6.18	73.31
Over 700 - less or equal to	5	1.40	74.72
Over 800 - less or equal to	6	1.69	76.40
Over 900 - less or equal to	7	1.97	78.37
Over 1000	77	21.63	100.00
Total	356	100.00	

Appendix D

Table D1: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Major Marketing Strategies

Strategies	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative	Remarks
Marketing with a lower price	129	34.40	34.40	Respondents are mutually exclusive. Only major marketing strategies were considered.
Marketing for quality goods	108	28.80	63.20	
Goods sold at market price	105	28.00	91.20	
Marketing by price	27	7.20	98.40	
Price for Surviving	6	1.60	100.00	
Total	375	100.00		

Table D2: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Pricing Methods

Pricing methods	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative	Remarks
Mark up pricing	201	53.60	53.60	Respondents are mutually exclusive. Only the key pricing method has been considered for one
Demand and supply based	66	17.60	71.20	
Market price	96	25.60	96.80	
Break-even pricing	12	3.20	100.00	

Table D3: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Performer of Marketing Activities

Key person	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative	Remarks
Self	246	65.60	65.60	Responses are mutually exclusive. Respondents are requested to say, only key marketing person.
Husband	81	21.60	87.20	
Employees	27	7.20	94.40	
Relatives	12	3.20	97.60	
Partners and	9	2.40	100.00	

Table D4: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Preferred Advertisement Media

Media	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Newspapers	150	55.56	Respondents are mutually inclusive. 105 respondents (28%) informed that they did not do an advertisement for their products.
Local cable channel	60	22.22	
TV	15	5.56	
Signboard/billboard	165	61.11	
Leaflet/handbill	90	33.33	
Websites	39	14.44	

Table D5: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Sales Promotion

Sales promotion	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Price reduction	105	60.34	Responses are mutually inclusive. 201 respondents (53.6%) did not use sales promotions.
Seasonal outlet	36	20.69	
Gifts	24	13.79	
Free delivery	15	8.62	
Others	90	51.72	

Table D6: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Sources of Market Information

Information sources	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage	Remarks
Customers	204	54.00	54.00	Respondents are mutually exclusive. Major information sources were considered. 285 respondents (76%) were not satisfied with existing information sources.
Suppliers	36	10.00	64.00	
Competitors	24	6.00	70.00	
Personal source	111	30.00	100.00	
Total	375			

Table D7: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Other Marketing Strategies

Activities	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Trade fair participation	111	30.00	Respondents are mutually exclusive. The total respondents were 375.
Foreign trade participation	63	17.00	
Personal selling adoption	114	30.00	
Market Research involvements	36	10.00	

Table D8: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Marketing Related Problems

Types of problems	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
The high expense of marketing	186	55.00	Respondents are mutually exclusive. Only the major problem has been considered for each respondent. 36 respondents reported that they do not have marketing problems.
Lack of training	33	10.00	
Transportation problem	42	12.00	
Lack of information and/or	42	12.00	
Lack of salesmen	36	11.00	
Total	339	100.00	

Table D9: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Number of Employees

Total employees	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
1-5	97	25.87	25.87
6-10	120	32.00	57.87
11-15	51	13.60	71.47
16-20	35	9.33	80.80
21-25	10	2.67	83.47
26-30	11	2.93	86.40
31-35	7	1.87	88.27
36-40	10	2.67	90.93
41-45	0	0.00	90.93
46-50	11	2.93	93.87
51 and above	23	6.13	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table D10: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Number of Female Employees

Female employees	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative percentage
Less than 5	240	64.00	64.00
6-10	61	16.27	80.27
11-15	18	4.80	85.07
16-20	8	2.13	87.20
21-25	5	1.33	88.53
26-30	6	1.60	90.13
31-35	7	1.87	92.00
36-40	6	1.60	93.60
41-45	0	0.00	93.60
46-50	3	0.80	94.40
51 and above	21	5.60	100.00
Total	375	100.00	

Table D11: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Employees' Monthly Minimum Salary

Salary (BDT)	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative	Remarks
0 - 1000	12	3.28	3.28	Respondents were mutually exclusive. Nine respondents did not answer the question.
Over 1000 - 3000	81	22.13	25.41	
3<4	138	37.70	63.11	
4<5	36	9.84	72.95	
5<6	93	25.41	98.36	
6<7	6	1.64	100.00	
Total	366			

Table D12: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Employees' Monthly Maximum Salary

Salary (BDT in	Responde	Percentag	Cumulative	Remarks
<3	15	4.46	4.46	Respondents were mutually exclusive. 39 respondents did not answer.
3<5	9	2.68	7.14	
5<7	102	30.36	37.50	
7<9	57	16.96	54.46	
9<11	63	18.75	73.21	
11<13	24	7.14	80.36	
13<15	0	0.00	80.36	
15<17	30	8.93	89.29	
17<19	9	2.68	91.96	
>20	27	8.04	100.00	
Total	336			

Table D13: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Employee's Incentives

Types of incentives	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Bonus	180	51.28	Responses are mutually inclusive. Out of 375, 352 respondents gave employees incentives. More than one response was considered for each respondent.
Overtime	105	29.91	
Lunch subsidies	45	12.82	
Free boarding	36	10.26	
Conveyance	24	6.84	
Free training (on the job)	30	8.55	

Appendix E

Table E1: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Access to Personal Computer

Number of PCs	Respondents	Percentage	Cumulative	Remarks
<3	156	55.91	55.91	Respondents are mutually exclusive. The average number of PCs is found 2 PCs per respondent. The maximum is found 30 PCs.
3<5	60	21.51	77.42	
5<7	9	3.23	80.65	
7<9	6	2.15	82.80	
9<11	21	7.53	90.32	
11<13	6	2.15	92.47	
13<15	6	2.15	94.62	
15<17	3	1.08	95.70	
17<19	3	1.08	96.77	
20 -above	9	3.23	100.00	
Total	279			

Table E2: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by ICT Usage

ICT Tools	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Uses Internet	210	56.00	Respondents were mutually inclusive.
Uses E-mail account	174	46.00	
Uses own business website	78	21.00	

Table E3: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by Accounting and Bookkeeping System

Category	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
Manual	204	59.00	Respondents are mutually exclusive. 30 respondents use a traditional single-entry system manually and 345 respondents use a double-entry system for their accounts and bookkeeping.
Computer-based	141	41.00	
Total	345	100.00	

Table E4: Distribution of Women Entrepreneurs by ICT Related Issues

Types of issues	Respondents	Percentage	Remarks
High price	171	49.14	Responses are mutually exclusive, the only major problem is considered for each respondent. Thirty (8%) respondents had found to have no ICT problems.
Frequent changes in technologies	42	12.07	
Lack of education and knowledge	51	14.66	
Lack of training	45	12.93	
Complex maintenance	24	6.90	

Lack of ICT personnel	15	4.31	
Total	348	100.00	

Appendix F

Table F1: Assessments of the Civil and Political Factors

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Policy for collaterals	5	22	26	58	14	125	321	330
SME Interest rate	1	17	31	65	11	125	307	
Administrative services	1	12	52	56	4	125	325	
Government assistances	1	46	30	43	5	125	374	
Law and order	0	14	36	66	9	125	305	
Tax-VAT-duties	0	22	56	44	3	125	347	

Table F2: Assessments of the Economic Factors

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Rate of inflation	1	37	52	31	4	125	375	375
Purchasing power	3	43	39	36	4	125	379	
Cost of inputs	3	36	29	53	4	125	356	
Cost of investment	5	58	29	29	4	125	404	
Market competition	4	48	33	33	7	125	384	
Business infrastructures	4	29	42	42	8	125	354	

Table F3: Assessments of the Social Factors

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Social values and perceptions	18	53	30	2	22	125	418	424
Recognitions and rewards	14	58	31	2	20	125	419	
Gender parities	10	70	27	1	17	125	429	
Social securities	18	53	36	2	16	125	430	

Table F4: Assessments of the Technological Factors

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Availability of technology	12	54	35	23	1	125	428	408
Cost of technology	6	52	43	22	2	125	399	
Technical skills	3	48	46	26	2	125	396	
Usage of technology	1	57	33	28	6	125	412	

Table F5: Assessments of the Legal Factors

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Availability of legal support	2	43	47	27	6	125	383	380
Cost of legal support	0	45	41	33	6	125	375	
Knowledge of industrial laws	1	42	52	25	5	125	383	

Table F6: Assessment of the Environment and Local Resources

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Availability of raw material	4	53	34	28	6	125	396	416
Availability of natural resources	8	57	40	20	0	125	428	
Climate	5	63	34	23	0	125	424	

Table F7: Assessments of the Human Resources

Factors assessed	Responses					Total	Aggregate value	Mean value
	Very good	Good	Indifferent	Nearly bad	Bad			
Human resources availability	6	74	35	9	1	125	450	435
Cost for human resources	12	48	33	29	3	125	410	
Skills of workers	15	61	27	22	0	125	444	

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